

Requirements for the Development of Data Management Plan Templates and Tools: A Scoping Review Protocol

Data Management Plan - FioDMP

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Administrative Information

Project Title:

Requirements for the Development of Data Management Plan Templates and Tools: A Scoping Review Protocol

Plan Visibility:

Privado

Step of DMP

Durante a execução do Projeto

Data de início do projeto:

03/2025

Language:

English

Abstract of project

Background: Although the FAIR Data Principles have guided international efforts to improve research data management, significant gaps still exist between the technical and social dimensions of their implementation in health-related contexts. Objective: This scoping review protocol aims to identify and synthesize the requirements for developing Data Management Plan (DMP) templates and DMP tools that are interoperable with data repositories, aligning them with the FAIR Principles and the researchers' practical needs. Methods: This protocol follows the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR). Searches will be conducted in PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, LILACS, and BRAPCI databases. Eligible studies will include literature addressing conceptual, technical, or sociotechnical aspects of DMP templates, DMP tools, and interoperability with research data repositories. Data will be charted thematically and synthesized through a narrative approach. Expected Outcomes: The review will identify existing approaches and gaps in the development of FAIR-aligned DMP templates and interoperable DMP tools, designed to connect with other research information systems, particularly data repositories. The findings are expected to provide an evidence base for developing a sociotechnical model that promotes sustainable, interoperable, and FAIR-oriented health data infrastructures.

Key-words

Data Management Plan; Data Repository; Requirements for Data Research; Research Data Management

Funder

- CNPq - Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico

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Data Description and Collection

Data Status:

Coletados e/ou Produzidos

The proposed scoping review will be conducted in accordance with the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews (Aromataris et al. 2024). For the presentation of results, the PRISMA extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) will be used (Tricco et al., 2018). It will follow the framework proposed by Arksey and O'Malley (2005), with the 5 stages: STEP 1: Identifying the research question, STEP 2: Identifying relevant studies, STEP 3: Study selection, Step 4: Data Charting, Step 5: Data Analysis and Presentation.

Data Types: Textuais

Data Formats: CSV, PDF, and XLS.

Approximate Volume: Less than 1 GB.

Metadata Standards: Dublin Core.

Storage and Sharing

Storage and Backup: Data will be stored in the Fiocruz Institutional Cloud Services and shared in the Harvard Dataverse Repositor, 4TU.ResearchData Repository and Fiocruz Data Repository.

Data Sharing: The research provides for data sharing.

Sharing Timeline: Data may be shared at the time of article publication.

License: CC-BY Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

Embargo: No embargo period is anticipated for the database or other data categories.

Legal and Ethical Requirements

Ethical Evaluation: The team is aware of the norms related to ethical evaluation in research.

Ethical Treatment: The research does not involve data processing that requires a specific ethical evaluation.

Data Protection: The team is familiar with legislation regarding the processing and protection of personal data.

Personal Data: The research does not involve the processing of personal data

Data Sharing

Does the research involve other categories of data that require an embargo period for availability? No.

Indicate the license to be applied to the database: CC-BY - Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

Does the research provide for data sharing? Yes.

Timeline: Data may be shared at the time of article publication.

Are there possible motivations for submitting the data to embargo periods in data sharing? No.